

Segmentation Analysis and Target Market Identification of Halal Tourism in Aceh Province

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to identify market segments and appropriate target markets for halal tourism in Aceh Province. The research method used is quantitative with data collection through questionnaires. The study findings show that Aceh Province has great potential as an attractive halal tourism destination, with the majority of respondents willing to pay more for high-quality halal tour packages. The study also identified different market segments with specific needs and preferences, which can help tourism industry players to develop targeted marketing strategies and products that meet the diverse needs of halal tourists. Suggested recommendations include development and promotion, provision of high-quality tour packages, increased awareness and visitation, targeted product development, provision of affordable travel options, and improved facilities and services. These recommendations are expected to help tourism industry players in Aceh Province to optimize the potential of halal tourism and increase Aceh's attractiveness as a global tourism destination.

KEYWORDS: Halal Tourism, Travelers, Segmentation, Target Markets

1. INTRODUCTION

Halal tourism has become a major focus in the development of the tourism sector in various countries, including Indonesia. Aceh Province, with its rich culture and Islamic heritage, has great potential to become a major halal tourism destination. In this context, segmentation strategies and target market identification are of key importance in understanding the preferences and needs of travelers seeking a shariah-compliant tourism experience. With the rapid growth of the tourism industry, it is important to understand the consumer behavior and preferences of potential markets. Through appropriate segmentation strategies, tourism industry players can identify market groups that have similar needs and preferences, to design appropriate and effective offerings.

In the context of halal tourism in Aceh Province, this study aims to investigate effective market segmentation strategies and identification of appropriate target markets for halal tourism. With a deep understanding of the preferences and needs of potential tourists, it is expected that effective marketing strategies can be formulated to increase the attractiveness of halal tourism destinations in Aceh Province, so as to maximize Aceh's potential as a world-class halal tourism destination.

2. LITERARUR REVIEW

2.1 Halal Tourism

Halal tourism aligns with Islamic teachings, encompassing sharia-compliant accommodations and food. It's a form of religious tourism that upholds Islamic behavior and lifestyle. As defined by Kemenpar (2012), it includes facilities that adhere to sharia principles. The Indonesian Ulema Council's definition (108/DSN-MUI/X/2016) extends to travel conforming to sharia, for recreation and self-improvement. Halal tourism integrates Islamic values, offering not just worldly enjoyment but also sharia compliance. It safeguards aspects like faith, intellect, lineage, and property, blending pleasure with religious devotion. This concept caters to the needs of Muslim travelers in both Muslim-majority and non-Muslim-majority countries, covering a broad spectrum of tourism activities beyond just religious ones.

2.2 Travelers

Tourists are defined as people visiting places outside their usual residence for varied purposes without seeking permanent residence or employment (Yoeti, 1985, p.123). The United Nations Economic and Social Council describes tourists as individuals who spend at least 24 hours in a destination country for various reasons, including holiday, health, research, religion, sports, business, or family

visits. According to A.J. Norwal, tourists are individuals who visit another country for non-employment purposes and spend money from sources outside the visited country. In Indonesia, as per Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 1969, a tourist is someone who travels for enjoying tourist experiences. The International Union of Official Travel Organization (IUOTO) categorizes tourists as visitors staying at least 24 hours but not more than 12 months for various personal or professional reasons, while excursionists are those who stay for less than 24 hours.

2.3 Market Segmentation

Kotler (2006) defines market segmentation as the division of a market into distinct groups of buyers that require separate products and/or marketing strategies. The importance of this strategy in tourism is to target each market segment specifically. Meanwhile, Yoety (2002) explains that market segmentation is grouping consumers into homogeneous groups, which are divided into four main categories: Geography, Socioeconomics and Demographics, Psychographics, and Behavior.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses quantitative methods defined by Siyoto and Sodik as research that involves extensive use of numbers from data collection, analysis, to presentation. The main objective, as explained by Hardani (2020), is to develop and apply mathematical models, theories, and hypotheses related to natural phenomena. According to Khusniyah & Hakim (2019), quantitative research is used as a characteristic approach that can generalize social phenomena that occur. By using a questionnaire survey in collecting data directly from respondents, it allows researchers to collect specific information related to demographics, perceptions, attitudes of tourists towards halal tourist destinations in Aceh.

4. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Segmentation Analysis

The questionnaire survey data collected amounted to 172 respondents with criteria who have an interest in halal tourism. Data collection consists of several aspects, namely demographics aspect, psychographics, preferences and needs, and potential to visit Aceh.

a. Demographics Aspect

Figure 1. Age

Figure 1 shows that halal tourism is highly attractive to young people, especially 21-30 years old, suggesting the use of digital media and social media in marketing strategies. For 31-40 years old, emphasis on family aspects and children's education is needed, while for those under 20 years old, educational and interactive programs can be developed. For the 41-50 and above 50 age group, a focus on convenience and accessibility is important.

Figure 2. Gender

Figure 2 shows the dominance of women in the halal tourism market with a percentage of 62.8%. This signifies the important role of women in halal travel decision-making, both individually and in the family context. Therefore, marketing strategies and product development should focus more on women's needs and preferences, including aspects of privacy, safety, and programs that support their spiritual and personal development.

Figure 3. Last Education

Figure 3 on the last education level shows the majority of high school graduates (44.8%), followed by bachelor's degree (36.0%) and diploma (16.3%). This indicates that halal tourism is attractive to a wide range of educational levels, especially popular among middle and higher educated people, who may have a deeper understanding of halal standards and Islamic values. Informative and knowledge-based marketing and educational materials could be an effective marketing tool for this segment.

Figure 4. Occupation

The graph shows that students (30.8%) are the largest segment interested in halal tourism, followed by private sector workers (29.7%), and self-employed (20.9%). This indicates a strong interest in halal tourism from those who are still in school and those

who are employed. The fact that students and college students are potential markets shows the opportunity for integration of halal tourism marketing with educational activities. The presence of a significant number of private workers and self-employed indicates an opportunity for customized halal tourism packages, as well as cooperation with companies for halal business travel packages.

Figure 5. Province of Origin

Figure 5 shows the distribution of interest in halal tourism based on the province of origin of respondents. DKI Jakarta and Central Java dominate as the largest source of respondents, indicating higher awareness or better access to information on halal tourism in these two regions. West Java and East Java also recorded significant numbers, confirming Java's role as a key market. Despite fewer respondents from Aceh, there are opportunities to improve marketing and education on halal tourism, requiring effective communication strategies to engage local communities in the development of halal tourism in Aceh.

Figure 6. Monthly Income Range

Figure 6 monthly income shows that most of the respondents have income below IDR 5 million, indicating that halal tourism should be offered at affordable prices for this market. For the segment with an income of IDR 5 million - IDR 10 million, there is a middle market opportunity that may be looking for value-added travel options. Meanwhile, the segment with income of more than Rp 10 million, although smaller, offers opportunities for premium halal tourism products and services.

b. Psychographics

Figure 7. Most Wanted Things when Traveling for Halal Tourism

Figure 7 highlights that spiritual and religious experiences are highly prioritized in halal tourism, followed by the importance of halal food and Islamic accommodation. This shows the importance of meeting halal standards in every aspect of travel. In addition, leisure and relaxation also received high ratings, indicating travelers' desire for a relaxing yet halal-compliant travel experience.

Figure 8. Frequency in Choosing Halal Facilities

Figure 8 shows that most of the respondents, 88 people, often choose tourist destinations based on the availability of halal facilities, giving the highest score of 5. This signifies the importance of halal facilities in their decision making. A score of 4 was also recorded high with 51 respondents, confirming the importance of this factor, albeit with some flexibility. The lower numbers for scores 1 to 3 suggest there are a small number of respondents who may place less importance on halal facilities in choosing a destination.

Figure 9. Factors Affecting the Decision to Choose a Halal Destination

Figure 9 highlights that information from social media and advertisements are most influential in choosing a halal travel destination, followed by recommendations from family and friends. This underscores the importance of digital marketing and direct recommendations in influencing consumer decisions. Online reviews and testimonials were also considered significant, demonstrating the huge influence of a destination's online reputation. Meanwhile, previous travel experience and price had a lower influence on the decision, indicating that cost or previous experience were not key considerations.

Figure 10. Information about Halal Destinations

Figure 10 shows that social media is the most important source of information about halal tourism destinations, with 143 respondents relying on it. Recommendations from family and friends also play an important role, emphasizing the value of social trust in decision making. Review sites such as TripAdvisor and Google Review follow in providing reliable information. While travel agents are still relevant, their usage is lower than other online sources.

Figure 11. Challenges when Searching for Halal Tourism Destinations

Figure 11 shows that respondents' main difficulty in finding halal travel destinations is getting accurate information, highlighting the importance of reliable sources of information. Other challenges include communicating with local communities, requiring a more inclusive and interactive approach, and higher travel costs. Lack of halal facilities and limited choice of destinations are also considerations, pointing to the need for more affordable and varied halal tourism options.

c. Preferences and Needs

Figure 12. Usual Travel Status

Figure 12 on travel status shows the majority of respondents traveled with family (43%), signaling the need for family-friendly tour packages in the halal tourism sector. Couples as travelers are also significant, indicating opportunities for romantic, halalcompliant travel experiences. Solo travelers and groups of friends are also significant, indicating potential for products that focus on individual adventures and group social activities. This suggests the need for halal tourism service providers to offer a diverse range of options to suit different types of travel.

Figure 13. Planning a Halal Tourism Trip

Figure 13 highlights that more than half of the respondents plan their halal tourism trips based on recommendations from friends or family, and an almost equal number plan their own through personal research. The use of tour packages from travel agents specializing in halal tourism is also quite popular. This trend reflects the desire for personal control in planning as well as the convenience offered by travel agents. Spontaneous planning is less common, indicating halal travelers' preference for more structured planning.

Figure 14. Frequency of Halal Tourism Travel

Figure 14 illustrates the frequency of halal tourism trips by respondents. The majority of respondents make such trips sometimes (1-2 times a year), while a smaller segment does it more often (more than 3 times a year). Some travel infrequently (less than 1 time a year), and some have never traveled but are interested. This indicates a large interest and potential market that may not be fully tapped for halal tourism.

Figure 15. Preferred Halal Activities

Figure 15 shows that halal culinary tourism is the activity that respondents are most interested in, emphasizing the important role of food in the halal tourism experience. This is followed by interest in visits to historical and cultural sites and outdoor activities, indicating a desire for experiences that involve exploring nature and culture. Spiritual activities were also quite prominent, emphasizing the importance of the religious aspect. Art and culinary workshops and adventure activities such as hiking or camping, although less popular, are still included in halal travel preferences.

Figure 16. Important Factors and Facilities when Choosing a Halal Tourism Destination

Figure 16 emphasizes that the main factors when choosing a halal tourist destination are cleanliness, comfort, and safety. Adequate prayer facilities and a variety of halal food options are also very important, indicating the need to meet the basic standards of Muslim travelers. While factors such as family recreational facilities, transportation, and parking are important, the top priority for halal travelers remains the aspect of basic Shariah compliance.

Figure 17. Importance of Halal Facilities

Figure 17 shows the importance of sharia facilities and services in tourism, with the highest score of 5 given by 123 respondents. This highlights that Shariah compliance is an important aspect of the travel experience, not just an add-on. Factors such as places of worship and halal food are key in respondents' travel decisions.

Figure 18. Budget Allocation for Travel

Figure 18 shows that 47.1% of respondents allocate a budget of IDR 1 million to IDR 3 million per trip, signaling a preference for budget travel. A total of 27.3% of respondents have budgets below Rp 1 million, emphasizing the demand for very affordable travel options. Only 9.3% allocated a budget of more than Rp 5 million, indicating that the market for premium travel is relatively limited.

Figure 19. Factors in Choosing Accommodation

Figure 19 shows that security, safety and affordability are the main factors for respondents in choosing halal accommodation or tour packages. Quality of service and customer experience, as well as adequate worship facilities are also very important. Privacy and comfort of accommodation are the next important considerations, while diverse and educational tour programs, as well as child-friendly family activities, are lower priorities, emphasizing the importance of basic factors such as safety, price, and shariah compliance are key in the decision to choose a halal tour package.

Figure 20. Willingness to Pay More for Halal Tourism Package

Figure 20 indicates that the majority of respondents, 93%, are willing to pay more for a high quality, well-equipped halal tour package. Only a small number, 7%, are not willing to pay more. This indicates that there is a sizable market for luxury halal tour packages that meet consumer expectations of facilities and services offered.

d. Potential to Visit Aceh

Figure 21. Respondents Who Have Settled in/Over Visited Aceh

Figure 21 shows that 44.2% of respondents have lived in or visited Aceh, while 55.8% have not. This indicates that most people may not be familiar with Aceh as a tourist destination, offering an opportunity to increase awareness and visitation through effective marketing and promotion.

Figure 22. Aspects Most Enjoyed in Aceh

Figure 22 shows that visitors who have been to Aceh particularly enjoy halal food and Acehnese culinary specialties, highlighting the importance of gastronomy in the tourism experience there. Aceh's natural beauty was also highly appreciated, while the cultural and historical heritage and hospitality of the local people received significant attention. Although spiritual experiences were considered lower, they remained an important aspect for some visitors.

Figure 23. Interest in Halal Travel to Aceh

Figure 23 indicates a very high level of interest from respondents to visit Aceh as a halal tourism destination, with most giving the highest score. This confirms a strong interest in Aceh. A score of 4 is also quite high, while scores of 1 to 3 are fewer, indicating the majority of respondents are very interested in visiting Aceh.

Figure 24. Motivation to Visit Aceh

Figure 24 reveals that cultural heritage and history are the main factors that attract people to visit Aceh, followed by hospitality and local culture. Aceh's natural beauty such as beaches and mountains also play an important role. Promotions and tour packages, as well as recommendations from friends or family, have less influence, highlighting the importance of cultural, social and natural elements in attracting tourists to Aceh.

Figure 25. Obstacles to Visiting Aceh

Figure 25 shows that cost is the main obstacle respondents face in traveling to Aceh, highlighting the importance of economic factors in travel decisions. Concerns related to safety and availability of information were also quite prominent, signaling the need to improve communication and safety infrastructure. Meanwhile, transportation and lack of interest were smaller but still important barriers, suggesting that access and marketing strategies could be improved to increase visitation to Aceh.

4.2. Target Markets Identification

Based on the segmentation analysis that has been carried out, 4 potential targets are obtained according to the travel category, namely:

Target	Criteria
Target 1 - Harmony Pairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographics: Couples, especially in the age of 31-40 years old, who are building their career and family. They are looking for a romantic travel experience that complies with halal values, and have varying education from high school/equivalent to university level; • Provinces of Origin: Potentially from provinces such as DKI Jakarta, Central Java, West Java and East Java; • Trip purposes: Romantic getaways, honeymoons, special celebrations; • Trip planning and travel arrangements: A structured plan, choosing accommodation or a halal tour package with security, safety and price in mind; • Psychographics and lifestyles: Prioritizing privacy, comfort and quality of service. Seeking memorable experiences to enrich relationships; • Special interests: Cultural tourism, natural beauty, halal food, romantic activities; • Technology uses: Actively use social media and travel apps for information, inspiration and experience sharing. The online reputation of the destination is an important consideration.
Target 2 - Buddy Crew	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographics: Groups of friends, usually young (21-30 years old) such as students, college students, or young professionals, who seek adventure and shared experiences in new destinations; • Provinces of origin: Potentially from provinces with high awareness of halal tourism such as DKI Jakarta, Central Java, West Java, and East Java;
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trip purposes: Exploration, adventure and social activities. They seek fun and memorable experiences to share with friends; • Trip planning and travel arrangements: Planning is often collective and spontaneous, with information seeking through social media and review sites; • Psychographics and lifestyles: Love socializing, adventure and cultural exploration. • Special interests: Outdoor activities, festivals, local performances, cultural sites. Interested in educational and diverse tours; • Technology uses: Highly connected to technology, they often use social media to share their experiences and seek inspiration for their next destination. They also rely on reviews.
Target 3 - Solo Rover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographics: Solo travelers, tend to be students and young professionals, aged 21-30. Often looking for a personalized experience; • Provinces of origin: They can come from various provinces, including DKI Jakarta, Central Java, Yogyakarta, South Kalimantan, Lampung, NTB, and Palembang; • Trip purposes: A combination of adventure, spiritual experience, and halal food and accommodation opportunities; • Trip planning and travel arrangements: Plan trips based on personal research and recommendations from family or friends, with a tendency to be independent but still value trusted advice;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychographics and lifestyles: Characteristic of seeking personal growth, adventure, and cultural experiences. Values flexibility and spontaneity in travel, while still prioritizing safety, affordability, and halal conformity; • Special interests: Interested in educational, diverse travel programs and activities that support personal reflection and spiritual growth; • Technology uses: Tend to be tech-savvy, using social media such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook for inspiration and information. Also rely on travel review sites like TripAdvisor and Google Reviews for informed decision-making about destinations and accommodation.
<p>Target 4 - Family Adventurers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographics: Families interested in halal tourism generally consist of parents with children aged between 31-40 years old. They are looking for destinations that provide fun and educational experiences for the whole family, while adhering to halal principles; • Provinces of origin: These families can come from various provinces in Indonesia such as DKI Jakarta, Central Java, Yogyakarta, South Kalimantan, Lampung, NTB, and Palembang; - Trip purposes: Spending quality time together, education for children, and spiritual experiences in line with halal values; • Trip planning and travel arrangements: Well-planned, prioritizing safety, comfort and affordability. Family-friendly accommodation and worship facilities; • Psychographics and lifestyles: Looking for fun and educational activities for all family members. Comfort and privacy are important factors in their trip; • Special interests: Educational tourism programs, child-friendly activities, and historical or cultural sites; • Technology uses: Social media for inspiration and information. Travel review sites like TripAdvisor and Google Reviews are also important in helping them make decisions about destinations and accommodation. Online travel booking apps are also often used to ease the booking process.

4.3. Positioning and Image for Each Selected Target Markets

Target 1: Harmony Pairs

- Positioning: “Aceh: Serenade of Serenity”. It offers a romantic and tranquil experience, attracting couples looking for a combination of privacy, natural beauty and cultural experiences.
- Image: Aceh is a paradise for couples, where they can enjoy natural beauty and culture in an atmosphere that supports halal values.

Target 2: Buddy Crew

- Positioning: “Aceh: The Adventure Hub”, for young groups who seek adventure and strengthen friendships with fun and social bonding activities such as outdoor (trekking, snorkeling, or surfing) and cultural (local festivals, cultural tours) activities.
- Image: As a gathering place for young energetic souls, seeking new and authentic experiences in an environment that supports halal principles.

Target 3: Solo Rover

- Positioning: “Aceh: Your Spiritual Exploration”, for solo travelers seeking a wealth of personal experiences, spiritual growth, and adventure.
- Image: As an ideal place for self- and spiritual exploration, it provides experiences that support self-reflection and spiritual pursuits, and offers comfort and safety for solo travelers.

Target 4: Family Adventurers

- Positioning: “Aceh: Family Halal Haven”, aimed at families looking for a fun and educational destination while adhering to halal principles.

- Image: As a family-friendly destination, it provides fun and educational activities for all family members, with guaranteed comfort and halal facilities.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Halal tourism in Aceh has significant potential, particularly among the younger generation and middle and upper secondary education. The high interest in halal tourism and willingness to pay more for a high-quality experience that complies with Islamic law indicates a strong market opportunity. Recommendations for further development to meet the specific needs of market segments for couples, groups/friends, solo travelers and families to tourism industry players in Aceh Province are as follows:

- **Development and Promotion:** Tourism industry players need to develop and promote Aceh Province as a halal tourism destination through effective marketing and promotion strategies. This can be done by utilizing Aceh's unique culture and rich Islamic heritage.
- **Provision of High-Quality Tour Packages:** There is a need to provide high quality halal tour packages that meet consumer expectations of the facilities and services offered. A focus on luxury experiences and service quality can be a key attraction.
- **Increased Awareness and Visitation:** Increase awareness and visitation to Aceh Province as a tourist destination through effective communication strategies. This could involve promotion through social media, cooperation with travel agents, and participation in tourism exhibitions.
- **Targeted Product Development:** It is necessary to develop targeted marketing strategies and products that meet the diverse needs of halal travelers. This includes the development of tour packages that suit the preferences of various market segments, such as couples, groups/friends, solo travelers.
- **Provision of Affordable Travel Options:** Provide affordable and value-added travel options for the middle-income segment. This may include competitively priced tour packages that offer attractive value adds.
- **Improved Facilities and Services:** Focus on improving facilities and services that meet safety, price, and Shariah compliance standards. This can include halal certification for accommodation and restaurants, as well as tourism infrastructure improvements.

These recommendations are expected to help tourism industry players in Aceh Province to optimize the potential of halal tourism and increase Aceh's attractiveness as a global tourism destination.

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